

and (III) exhibited a strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} for an isolated carbonyl group. It is a general observation in these reactions that the 3-oxo group is preferably more reactive than the 6-oxo groups⁶. Therefore the strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} is assigned

to $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}6-$ in compounds (II) and (III). The configuration at spirane carbon at C3 in compounds (II) and (III) was determined by ^1H nmr values. It has been found that in the case of isomer containing axial $\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond, ring methylene protons

($-\text{S}-\underset{\text{Spirane}}{\text{CH}_2}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$) signal is shifted downfield by $\delta 0.04-0.10$ ppm as compared to methylene protons signal where $\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond is equatorial⁷. Com-

parison of the ^1H nmr values for ring methylene protons in compounds (II) and (III) confirmed that C3- $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond is axial in (II) and equatorial in (III).

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Girinimbine and Koenimbine from *Murraya exotica* Linn.

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IN continuation of the investigation on *Murraya exotica* Linn. in our laboratory, from which coumarins¹⁻⁵, carbazoles⁶, flavonoids^{7,8} were reported, we now report two carbazoles, koenimbine (I) $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ and girinimbine (II) $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ from the same plant.

(I)

(II)

The alkaloids were obtained from the neutral fraction of the petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) extract of the stem bark of *M. exotica* on chromatography over alumina and characterised by ir and uv spectral data and also by direct comparison with authentic samples.

Though the yield of the first carbazole (I) is very low, the isolation and identification of koenimbine and girinimbine from *M. exotica* Linn. (a member of the genus *Murraya*) is important from taxonomic standpoint.

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Phenyl Hydrazine-N-Dithiocarbamate : A New Gravimetric Reagent for the Determination and Separation of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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ALTHOUGH a lot of work has been carried out on dithiocarbamates and on their analytical¹⁻⁷ applications, phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate has not been used in analytical field. Phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate has been employed as a new gravimetric reagent for the separation and

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determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) and the results are presented here.

Experimental

The potassium salt of the reagent was prepared by mixing the solutions of phenyl hydrazine and carbon disulphide in ether and KOH at ice cold temperature (molar ratio, phenyl hydrazine : carbon disulphide : KOH = 1 : 1 : 1). The 1% (w/v) solution of the reagent was prepared in distilled water.

Procedure for the determination of copper(II) : An aliquots of the standard solution (0.02M) of copper(II) was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and the pH was adjusted to 3.5-4 using acetate buffer. A 1% solution (w/v) of potassium phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate in distilled water was then added with stirring. A brown precipitate gradually separated out which was digested on a steam bath at 60-65° for about 10 min. The precipitate was filtered in a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed several time with distilled water. It was dried at 100-110° and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH-NHCS}_2)_2$. The results of the estimation are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER(II)

Sl. No.	Cu(II) taken mg	Weight of the complex mg	Cu(II) found mg	%error
1.	9.48	64.19	9.20	-0.2
2.	12.64	85.40	12.61	-0.23
3.	18.96	128.40	18.92	+0.18
4.	25.28	171.18	25.25	+0.11
5.	37.92	256.02	37.87	-0.22

Procedure for the determination of nickel(II) : A known volume of the nickel solution (0.02M) was diluted to 100 ml with distilled water and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.5-4.0 by using acetate buffer. A three fold excess of 1% solution (w/v) of the reagent was added. A green precipitate gradually separated out which was digested on steam bath at 50-60° for about 15 min. The precipitate was filtered in a sintered glass crucible (G-4), repeatedly washed with distilled water, dried at 100-105° and weighed as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH-NHCS}_2)_2$. The results of the estimation are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL(II)

Sl. No.	Ni(II) taken mg	Weight of the complex mg	Ni(II) found mg	%error
1.	8.7	62.88	8.68	-0.22
2.	11.6	83.86	11.58	-0.17
3.	17.4	126.14	17.42	+0.12
4.	23.2	167.70	23.16	-0.21
5.	34.8	252.28	34.84	+0.09

Effect of foreign ions : Determination of copper(II) was carried out in presence of several anions and cations. The anions Br^- , F^- , CN_2^- ,

$\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, BO_3^- , tartarate, citrate and EDTA in three-fold excess did not interfere in the determination of copper(II). The interference of Ni(II), Co(III), Fe(II), Fe(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), Sn(II), Mg(II), Al(III), In(III), Ga(III), Th(IV) and U(VI) has been avoided by using an ammoniacal mixture of (0.1M) tartarate and (0.1M) EDTA. Oxotitanium(IV) and oxo-vanadium(IV) were masked by adding sodium flouride. In the determination of copper(II) in presence of the above ions, the masking agent was added prior to the addition of the reagent, the mixture gently heated and the pH adjusted to 3.5-4.0 by acetate buffer.

Separation and determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) from their mixture : When copper and nickel ions were present together in a solution, copper was precipitated first as Cu(II) dithiocarbamate in the presence of ammoniacal solution of tartarate and EDTA. Thereafter the nickel in the filtrate was demasked by employing conc. HNO_3 and determined as Ni dithiocarbamate.

A mixture containing copper(II) and nickel(II) was taken into a 500 ml beaker and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water. Appropriate amounts (0.01M) of ammoniacal solution of tartarate and EDTA were added and the mixture gently heated for 5 min. The pH of the solution was maintained at 3.5-4.0 using acetate buffer. One percent reagent solution (w/v) was then added with constant stirring. The brown precipitate of Cu(II) dithiocarbamate was digested on a steam bath for 10 min and allowed to settle for an hour. The precipitate was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as described above.

The filtrate containing nickel(II) ions was concentrated to 25% of the total volume. 10 ml of conc. nitric acid (AR) was added on cooling and the solution evaporated to dryness, diluted with distilled water (10 ml) and again evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with 100 ml of distilled water. Any adherent nitric acid was just neutralised with ammonia solution. The solution was gently heated for 5 min. The pH of the solution was maintained at 3.5-4.0 using acetate buffer and 1% reagent solution (w/v) was added. The grey precipitate of nickel dithiocarbamate was digested at 50-60° for 15 min on a steam bath and allowed to settle for 2 hr. The precipitate was filtered in sintered crucible (G-4) and determined as described earlier. The results of the estimation of copper(II) and nickel(II) are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The copper(II) complex is insoluble in methanol, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, amyl alcohol and isopropyl alcohol and quite soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide and morpholine. It has been observed that the complex was stable in between 110-120°. When heated in an oven at different temperatures above 120° it decomposes slowly.

The nickel complex is quite soluble in acetone, dioxane, nitrobenzene, dimethyl sulphoxide and

TABLE 3—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF COPPER(II) AND NICKEL(II)

Sl. No.	Cu(II) mg	Ni(II) mg	Cu complex mg	Ni complex mg	Cu(II) found mg	Ni(II) found mg	%error for Cu(II)	%error for Ni(II)
1.	9.48	8.7	64.10	62.80	9.46	8.67	-0.21	-0.31
2.	12.64	17.4	85.98	125.80	12.61	17.37	-0.23	-0.17
3.	12.64	23.2	85.34	167.62	12.60	23.14	-0.31	-0.25
4.	37.92	43.5	256.00	314.2	37.81	43.14	-0.29	-0.27
5.	47.40	23.2	320.4	167.64	47.32	23.14	-0.16	-0.25

morpholine and is stable at 100-110°. It decomposes slowly above 110°.

The presence of Ag(I), Pb(II) and Bi(III) interferes in the determination of copper(II).

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Semicarbazide as a New Reagent for the Detection of Silver(I)

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NUMEROUS organic reagents¹⁻¹⁰ form complexes with silver(I) but most of them are not selective.

Only *p*-dimethylamino benzylidene rhodanine⁵ and dithiozone⁶ have been found to be more selective for the drop analysis of silver(I). The present study, which is based on the reaction of semicarbazide with silver(I) in nitric acid medium has been used for the detection of silver(I) only on a qualitative basis. The reagent is not suitable for quantitative determination of silver because of the limited stability of the complex. The method is cold operated and instantaneous.

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Experimental

Materials: Silver nitrate and semicarbazide (both B.D.H.) and other reagents of either B.D.H. or E. Merck grade were used. The cations were used as nitrates or carbonates while the anions were used as sodium or potassium salts. A micrometer syringe was used for measuring the drop volume while graduated droppers were employed for adding the solutions of the interfering ions. Silver nitrate stock solution (2 µg/ml) and semicarbazide solution (0.1% w/v) were prepared in double distilled water. The solutions of interfering ions were either in double distilled water or in 0.01N nitric acid. Hilger Unispeck Spectronic 20 was used for measuring absorbance.

Procedure:

(i) **Spot test:** A drop of silver(I) solution (2 µg/ml) was taken on a black spot plate and one drop of 0.01 N nitric acid was added followed by a drop of 0.1% aqueous solution of the reagent. A white precipitate formed instantaneously, which gradually turned to grey violet. This indicated the presence of silver(I). In another similar test, a drop of 2% manganous nitrate solution followed by a drop of 2.5 N sodium hydroxide solution was added soon after the formation of the white precipitate. A black stain was obtained. Sensitivity: 2 µg/ml, concentration limit: 4 : 100000.

(ii) **Spectrophotometric method:** A 5 ml of aliquot, containing 0.8-6 µg/ml of silver was taken in a 25 ml measuring flask to which 2 ml of 0.01 N nitric acid and 15 ml of 0.1% aqueous reagent were added. The volume was made up to the mark with double distilled water. The absorbance was measured within 40 min at 520 nm against reagent blank.

Discussion

The system silver-semicarbazide absorbs maximum at 520 nm and the reagent has nil absorbtion at this wavelength. The molar absorptivity, ϵ is found to be 8.6×10^3 lit. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The range of pH value for no change in absorption has been found to be 1-7. So a pH of 4 was selected. Four fold excess of reagent over silver is required for full colour development, but further excess does not affect absorbance. Beer's law is obeyed upto 6 µg/ml of silver. Sandell's sensitivity of reaction comes to 0.0056 µg/cm². For 6 aliquots of standard solution (6 µg/m of silver), the standard deviation and relative deviation have been found to be